

“Full Paper-NUMERICAL EXPERIMENTAL STUDY ON INFLUENCE OF MULTIWALLED CARBON NANOTUBE ON MIXED MODE FRACTURE OF SANDWICH COMPOSITE”

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ABSTRACT

Performance of sandwich composites using multi-walled carbon nanotube (MWCNT) doped resin system under mixed mode loading is investigated through both numerical and experimental analyses. Finite element analysis for the mixed mode bending (MMB) sandwich specimen was performed with Abaqus Standard cohesive zone model and crushable foam hardening properties assuming surface to surface standard interaction between face sheet and core. Finite element analysis was followed with experimental investigation on mixed mode fracture toughness of glass-epoxy poly vinyl chloride (PVC) core sandwich composite panels with and without MWCNT using mixed mode bending setup. The fracture performance of specimens with 0.2 weight percentage of MWCNT in terms of mixed mode delamination fracture toughness (G_{MMB}) is observed to be improved significantly over samples without MWCNT for mode ratio 0.8 in both numerical and experimental investigations. A simple method of sonication is adopted for dispersion of MWCNT in epoxy resin in this study. This is an easy and cost effective methodology used for vacuum resin infusion (VRI) technology in comparison to previously adopted other methods limited to laminated composites. Initial delamination was introduced by 80 μm thick Teflon sheet between face sheet and core. Improvement of 38.61% in mixed mode fracture toughness mean value with a standard deviation of 7.85% over that of conventional sample for 0.2wt% of MWCNT (taken as the percentage of total weight of epoxy resin) was recorded for mode ratio 0.8. The study demonstrates good correlation between numerical and experimental analyses supported by high resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) and field emission scanning electron microscope (FESM) analyses.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sandwich composite structures are used in several engineering applications for their primary advantage of higher strength to weight ratio. In spite of several advantages, sandwich composites are sensitive to interfacial delamination. Debonding between face sheet and core (delamination) imposes a serious threat to these structures by impairing structural integrity and load bearing efficiencies. Moreover, sandwich structures are subjected to mixed mode delamination failures in most of the engineering applications. Delamination fracture toughness of unidirectional glass/epoxy composites for mixed mode bending (MMB) is addressed by Benzeggagh and Kenane along with development of B-K criteria [1]. This

principle of MMB test is extended for debond propagation in foam cored sandwich specimen [2,3]. Finite element analysis (FEA) for mixed mode delamination in composite materials is reported in literature [4]. On the other hand, improvement in mode I, mode II and/or mixed mode fracture toughness using MWCNT are reported in literatures [5-11], but those are primarily limited to laminated composites. To the best of authors' knowledge there appears to be no work done on numerical experimental investigation on effect of lower percentage of sonicated MWCNT dispersed resin system on mixed mode fracture toughness of glass-epoxy (G/E) polyvinyl chloride (PVC) core sandwich composites which is addressed in this study.

2 MANUFACTURING OF SAMPLES

PVC foam with density 100 kg/m^3 and 30mm thickness of trade name Divinycell H100 supplied by DIAB Inc. was used for the manuscript. PVC foam core was covered by a layer of glass fiber stitched combination mat followed by a layer of woven roving mat (WRM) on both top and bottom was enclosed air-tight in a vacuum bag fitted with inlet and outlet pipes. Epoxy resin (Airstone 780E of Dow Chemicals with 1400 mPas viscosity and 1.15 g/cc density at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and hardener (Airstone 785H of Dow Chemicals with 13 mPas viscosity and 0.94 g/cc density at $25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) in 30wt% of epoxy resin are mixed by stirring at 150 rpm for 15 min. In case of CNT sonicated samples, The resin is mixed with MWCNT in different wt% of epoxy resin using a sonicator (500 W, 20 kHz Vibracell Liquid processor) for 2.5 hours intermittently at room temperature ($25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$) and then mixed with the above hardener as stated above to prepare the resin system. The samples are casted through VRI technology with the prepared resin system and allowed to cure for more than 48 hours at room temperature ($25 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Initial delamination was provided with $80 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ thick non-stick impermeable Teflon sheet by coating the upper surface of the core. The sample with required dimensions (length (L) = 170 mm, width (b) = 25 mm, and thickness (T) = 35 mm) and the pre-crack were prepared from these casted sandwich plates.

3 NUMERICAL INVESTIGATION

3.1 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF DCB TEST

Finite element analysis was done with Abaqus Standard cohesive zone model and crushable foam hardening properties assuming surface to surface interaction between face sheet and core. Two dimensional plane strain model of DCB specimen was modelled using 1892 nodes, 1615 4-noded bilinear CPE4 plane strain quadrilateral solid elements (based on convergence study) in Abaqus standard version 6.14. The dimensions and material properties of the GFRP face sheet and PVC foam core used represent those obtained from the experimental program. The modulus of elasticity and Poisson's ratio of the GFRP face sheets and the foam core were calculated from the experimental investigations carried out on the component parts as per ASTM D3039/D3039M-14. The experimentally determined material properties are as listed in Table 1 below:

Description of parameters	Face sheet (E _f) MPa		PVC Core (E _c) MPa	
	Mean Value	StdDev (%RSD)	Mean Value	StdDev (%RSD)
Modulus of Elasticity	10724	5.17	70	1.44
Poisson's Ratio (ν_{12})	0.17	9.08	0.336	1.96

Table 1. Material properties used for the simulation

Face-sheet was fabricated with two alternate layers of 995 gsm stitched combination mat (WRM stitched and assembled with Chopped Strand mats (CSM) of glass fibers) and 1161 gsm resin treated plain Woven Roving glass fiber mat (WRM). The face sheets are assumed to be isotropic with the properties shown above for the chopped strand mats are stitched with WRM. The foam core of much lower yield stress than that of glass fibers is modelled with crushable foam hardening properties for it exhibits plasticity during deformation.

Initial debond of 48 mm between the top face sheet and the core equal to that provided for experimental investigation as a pre-crack was introduced in the sample for numerical analysis also. Cohesive contact was assigned between the top face sheet and core excepting portion for initial delamination (where no contact was assigned). A tied-contact was provided between core and face sheet at bottom throughout the entire length. Assuming a cohesive layer between the top face sheet and core is a simplification of the crack propagation in a smeared layer of face sheet and core. The interaction properties were assigned through prescribing the cohesive behavior, damage properties with fracture toughness and fracture criteria and a quadratic traction. The normal fracture energy was calculated using modified compliance calibration technique using a value of the exponent n as 2.22 (as obtained from Compliance versus crack length plot). The normal fracture energy was calculated to be 898 J/m^2 (with relative standard deviation (RSD) 1.62%) for conventional sample and 1165 J/m^2 (for particular sample) for sample with 0.2 wt% MWCNT were used for the numerical study. The boundary conditions similar to experimental set up were used for the simulation. The damage initiation value can not be determined by the experiment and adopted to be 1.2 MPa and 1.6 MPa for conventional and CNT- samples respectively from previous simulations of the authors and found to be correlated well with the experimental results. Displacement control condition on the nodes of face sheets was adopted for the simulation. The deflected shape of the simulated DCB specimen for conventional sample and that with the parameters for sample with 0.2 wt% of MWCNT are shown in Fig.1 and Fig. 2 respectively.

Figure 1. Deflected shape of the simulated DCB specimen for conventional sample

Figure 2: Deflected shape of the simulated DCB specimen for sample with 0.2wt% MWCNT

The deflected shape of the face sheet shown in figure is after 69 increments for conventional sample and 78 increments for samples with MWCNT respectively and completion of the analysis. The strain contour plot shows that the fracture is mode I dominating type associated with a slight mode mixity at the crack tip.

3.2 EXPERIMENTAL INVESTIGATION

Sandwich samples of dimensions 170mm X 25 mm X 36 mm were cut from the initially manufactured plates. The length of initial debond was kept within 48 ± 1 mm. Instron Electropulse 1000 UTM with pneumatic grips and 1 kN load cell was used to apply tensile load to the specimens at a cross-head speed of 0.5 mm/min through Aluminum hinge tabs attached on both faces (top and bottom) of sandwich samples up to a crack propagation of at least 20 mm from the point of crack initiation. The load versus displacement data at discrete propagation points were recorded by a software utility service of the computer attached to the UTM whereas the crack propagation was recorded through camera attachments.

The load displacement plots for the simulated DCB specimen superposed with that of the typical experimental result of the conventional sample is shown in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Simulated load-disp plot superposed with that of experimental result for neat sample

Figure 4: Simulated load-disp plot superposed with that of experimental result for sample with 0.2 wt% MWCNT

The figures show a good agreement in the initial linear portion of the plots which is an expected result. The minor difference in the non linear portion is due to the slight variation in assumptions (using mean value of normal fracture energy instead of that of the particular experimental sample superposed) made in simulation than reality and for this reason, the simulated peak load is slightly more than the experimental one. The post peak stick and slip nature of the experimental plot is due to the crack propagation through smeared layer of face sheet and core which is not so prominent in the simulated plot for assuming a cohesive layer between the isotropic (as assumed in the simulation) top face sheet and the PVC core.

The plots show good match in initial portion. The greater stiffness and peak load of the CNT samples in the nonlinear part is due to the resistance offered by the MWCNT against crack initiation and propagation over that of non-CNT samples. The displacement ductility in the post peak portion is observed to be more in the CNT samples in comparison to the samples without MWCNT.

3.3 FINITE ELEMENT MODELLING OF MMB SPECIMEN

The FEM model of MMB test setup consisted of two face sheets, a core and a loading lever and two rollers. The Face sheets and core were of length 180 mm and 35 mm width. The core was 30 mm thick and the face sheets were each 2.5 mm thick. These were the dimensions of the specimen on which the MMB tests were performed.

The Setup was modelled as a 2D plane Strain model. The model consists of 3116 nodes and 2668 CPE4 (A 4-node bilinear plane strain quadrilateral) elements and 45 CPE3 (3 node bilinear plane strain triangular) elements. Two Surface to surface interactions were defined for both top face- core bond and bottom face-core bond. And an interaction property defining the face core bond characteristics was assigned to these two interactions. The interaction between the top face-core is assigned such that the initial crack is introduced as per the experimental data. The interaction property contained 'cohesive behaviour' and 'Damage', where the fracture toughness and fracture criteria have been assigned. Quadratic traction was used for damage initiation.

Finite element analysis for the mixed mode bending (MMB) sandwich specimen was performed with Abaqus Standard cohesive zone model and crushable foam hardening properties assuming surface to surface standard interaction between face sheet and core. The deflected shape is shown in Figure 5. Finite element analysis was followed with experimental investigation on mixed mode fracture toughness of glass-epoxy poly vinyl chloride (PVC) core sandwich composite panels with and without MWCNT using mixed mode bending setup. The fracture performance of specimens with 0.2 weight percentage of MWCNT in terms of mixed mode delamination fracture toughness (G_{MMB}) is observed to be improved significantly over samples without MWCNT for mode ratio 0.8 in experimental investigations. A simple method of sonication is adopted for dispersion of MWCNT in epoxy resin for this study. This is an easy and cost effective methodology used for vacuum resin infusion (VRI) technology in comparison to previously adopted other methods limited to laminated

composites. Initial delamination was introduced by 80 μm thick Teflon sheet between face sheet and core. Improvement of 38.61% in mixed mode fracture toughness mean value with a standard deviation of 7.85% over that of conventional sample for 0.2wt% of MWCNT (taken as the percentage of total weight of epoxy resin) was recorded for mode ratio 0.8. The study demonstrates good correlation between numerical and experimental analyses supported by high resolution transmission electron microscope (HRTEM) and field emission scanning electron microscope (FESM) analyses. Sample micrographs of CNT dispersed in the resin system at the interface of sandwich composite is shown in Figure 6 which indicate that the randomly dispersed sonicated multi walled carbon nanotubes (MWCNT) within the resin system of the interface between face sheet and core improves the resistance against face core debond under mixed mode loading due better mechanical interlocking among the constituents of the interface.

Figure 5: Deflected shape of the simulated MMB sample

Figure 6: Micrographs of CNT dispersed in the resin system at the interface of sandwich composite: (a) Interface region at 85 k magnification showing CNT on fractured GFRP sheet , (b) CNT bridging two resin systems at 85 k magnification,

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